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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with great pride and enthusiasm that we present the maiden edition of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities*, published by the Gamji Institute for Training and Research. This inaugural publication marks a significant milestone in our commitment to fostering academic excellence and contributing to the scholarly discourse in various fields of study.

The articles featured in this edition represent a diverse range of research topics, each offering valuable insights and advancing our understanding of critical issues. The depth and breadth of the studies reflect the dedication and scholarly rigor of the authors, and we are honored to showcase their work.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to the authors for their invaluable contributions and to the peer reviewers for their diligent efforts in ensuring the quality and integrity of the research presented. We also express our appreciation to the editorial board and support staff whose dedication and hard work have made this publication possible.

As we embark on this scholarly journey, we invite readers to engage with the research presented in this journal, to reflect on the insights offered, and to contribute to the ongoing dialogue in their respective fields. We look forward to future editions and the continued growth of the *Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities* as a platform for academic excellence and intellectual exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Aminu Ahmad

Chairman, Editorial Board

Gamji Journal of Arts and Humanities

Gamji Institute for Training and Research

IMPACT OF ELECTRICITY POWER OUTAGE ON MANUFACTURING PERFORMSANCE IN NIGERIA: A TIME SERIES APPROACH (1985 – 2022)

By

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at investigating the impact of electricity outage on manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on the annual data covering the period 1985 – 2022, unit root (*ADF*) test was carried out. The stationary property of the variables at different significance levels i.e. at level and first difference $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ necessitate the use of *ARDL* model and granger causality analysis. The result of the autoregressive distributed lag (*ARDL*) model revealed that electricity consumption (*ELC*) and electricity generation (*ELG*) has a negative and significant impact, while labor employment (*LEP*) and gross capital formation was found have positive (significant) and negative (insignificant) impact on the manufacturing performance in Nigeria in the short run. In addition, the causality analysis revealed uni-directional causality telling how manufacturing performance is immensely affected by electricity power outage in Nigeria. Thus, it was recommended that an adequate supply of electricity is not only crucial for the growth of the manufacturing sector but also for the overall economic development of the country, paving way for rapid economic advancement, and enabling Nigeria to realize its full potential.

Keyword: Electricity consumption, electricity generation, gross capital formation, labor employment, Manufacturing performance, *ARDL*, Cointegration, Causality analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because its operations have an impact on economic productivity, the manufacturing sector is a major part of the industry. Because of its productive capability to supply the economy's aggregate demand, the sector is essential for economic sustainability. In the modern economy, the manufacturing sector is a catalyst and offers a host of dynamic benefits that are essential for economic development. A typical advanced nation has a manufacturing sector that leads in several areas. Through import substitution and export growth, it can boost productivity; generate foreign exchange earning potential, and increase employment and per capita income in the home economy. Moreover, it generates investment capital at a rate quicker than any other economic sector and fosters deeper and more robust connections between other industries that drive economic expansion. Anyanwu (2000) asserts that the manufacturing sector dominates the GDP and has expedited Nigeria's economic expansion.

It is a known truth that the manufacturing sector functions better when there is a thriving energy industry; as a result, the expansion of the manufacturing sector is stimulated by a steady supply of electricity. Essentially, the expansion of the manufacturing sector and the industrial sector as a whole depends on a sufficient supply of electricity. However, things are different in Nigeria, where a lack of electricity has stunted the expansion of the manufacturing sector and reduced its share of the country's GDP. The percentage of the GDP attributable to the manufacturing sector decreased from 7.84 percent in 1971–1980 to 7.33 percent in 1981–1990. Between 1991 and 2000, and between 2001 and 2010, this percentage fell to 4.87 and 3.84 percent, respectively. Similarly, between 2011 and 2019 the manufacturing sector averagely contributed 9.4% of GDP (CBN, 2019).

Nigeria produced and transmitted an average of 4,000 Mega Watts (MW) in 2020, according to KPMG (2021), with an average of 3,000 MW being delivered to energy users nationwide (but the generation rarely exceeded 5,000 MW). This performance in the power value chain was mostly impacted by infrastructure deficiencies. According to Henry, Ndem, Ujong, & Ihuoma (2021) and KPMG (2021) there is a severe shortage of energy in the existing supply to meet the demands of manufacturers and the general public.

To make matters worse, according to World Bank (2021a), only 57% of Nigerians have access to electricity, compared to 100% in Mauritius and Tunisia, 99.8% in Egypt, 99.1% in Algeria, 99% in Morocco and the Seychelles, 96.1 % in Cape Verde, 90.7 % in Gabon, 84.3 % in Ghana, and 84.2 % in South Africa. Owing to these circumstances, Nigeria has the largest energy access deficit in the world (World Bank, 2021b). An estimated \$26.2 billion (N10.1 trillion) in annual economic losses, or around 2% of the World Bank's 2021 GDP, are a result of the manufacturing sector's company expansion being impeded by the absence of electricity supplies. The manufacturing sector in Nigeria faces substantial obstacles due to its poor ranking of 171 out of 190 countries in the 2020 World Bank Doing Business reports for electricity access. (World Bank, 2021b).

Despite the above, the sector has not performed as expected and hence necessitated for the researches of this nature in order to examine the impact of electricity power outage on the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria covering 1985 – 2022 period.

However, few studies were conducted on the electricity power outage and performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This study aims at adding to the existing arguments in the literature on the impact of electricity power outage on manufacturing performance in Nigeria using Engle-Granger and ARDL approach.

The paper is divided into five sections. Section one covers Introduction aspect. Section two present the literature review. Section three describes the research methodology. Section five is the data presentation, conclusion and recommendation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ekene and Mbobo (2019) used the ordinary least squares (OLS) technique to examine the effect of power outages on manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria using data from 1980 to 2018. The result showed that electricity supply exerts a positive-significant impact on manufacturing output. It was recommended that the exchange rate be stabilized to avoid shocks affecting the prices of imported equipment used by energy-generating agencies.

Similarly, Iwashokun (2019) employed the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) and Toda-Yamamoto techniques to appraise various sources of energy supply and manufacturing output in Nigeria using data from 1981 to 2016. The result showed that hydroelectricity, gas and coal have a positive-significant link with manufacturing output in the short and long runs. In addition, the result also showed that all the energy sources investigated granger caused manufacturing output.

Sabo and Lekan (2019) examine the effect of controlling firm characteristics in the energy- business growth relationships in their paper by employing quantitative methodology. Multi- stage sampling was applied to collected data from three stratum i.e. manufacturing, hotel & restaurant and wholesale & retail sector SMEs. The reliability of the measurement model is tested using Chronbach Alpha while multiple linear regression model is used to test the hypothesis. It was found that, the relationship is positively strong between SMEs growth, electricity supply and firm age whereas firm size and leverage had a similar less relationships. The paper based on the empirical findings recommends that there is an urgent need to improve electricity supply to SMEs in order to accelerate the growth of enterprises and by extension the economy.

Shaibu and Oyarebu-Shaibu (2019) in their work investigates the maintenance productivity in the electricity industry in Nigeria from 1996 to 2015. The data was generated from United States Energy Information Administration (USEIA), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET) and Transparency International (TI). The fully modified ordinary least squares (FM-OLS) technique was used for estimation. The results from the study showed that that amount of rainfall (weather condition), corruption, electricity retail price (tariff structure), government expenditure (funding), labour (manpower availability) and vandalism all have significant and varying effects on maintenance productivity of the electricity industry in Nigeria. It is recommended that policies directed at improving the performance of electricity service should largely consider the impacts of these variables.

Teega and Ahiakwo (2019) conducted a research to evaluate electrical power outages in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Analysis is made using reliability and customer indices. The mean time between failures (MTBF), mean time to failure (MTTF) and availability were used as variables of the study. Investigations were carried out to ascertain the causes of circuit

breaker trip, transformer failure, transmission line failure and bus bar failure. The result showed that for the period under study, circuit breaker trip the most due to overload, short circuit and ground fault followed by transformer and transmission line failures. It further revealed that the feeders were progressively overloaded as the population in the city increased. This resulted in a low per customer availability of power supply. It is evident that the analysis provided the guide and hence recommendation to sustain every supply to users in Port Harcourt was made.

Adelegan and Otu (2020) examined how Nigeria's industrial output was affected by energy use. The study used data from 1980 to 2018 and the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach. The findings showed that the consumption of gas, electricity, and petroleum products had a direct and significant impact on industrial output over both the short and long terms. In the short term, however, there was little or no correlation between industrial output and electricity use. It was advised that the government take advantage of the abundance of natural gas and invest in other energy sources.

Fakih et al. (2020) in their work examines the effects of power outages on the performance of manufacturing firms in the MENA region. They employed a firm-level dataset from the World Bank's Enterprise Surveys (WBES) database. The extents of power outages are represented by objective measures characterizing durations and frequencies of power outages, and by perception-based measures reflecting firms' perceived severity of power outages. Firm performance is represented by employment, sales, and productivity growth rates. The outcomes emphasize the adverse consequences of power outages for the performance of manufacturing firms in the MENA region. It was suggested that diverse patterns of power outages have varying implications for firm performance, and that the effects of power outages exhibit variations with firm size.

Fried & Lagakos (2020) carried out a research on general equilibrium approach of electricity and firm productivity by building a dynamic macroeconomic model to study the long-run effect. Power outages lower productivity in the model by creating idle resources, by depressing the scale of incumbent firms and by reducing entry of new firms. The model also predicts that the short-run partial equilibrium effects of eliminating outages are small. However, the long-run general equilibrium effects are many times

larger, supporting the view that eliminating outages is an important development objective.

Onwe and King (2020) investigated the connection between Nigeria's manufacturing sector's production and electricity usage. The autoregressive distributed lagged model (ARDL) and data from 1981 to 2019 were used in the study. The findings showed that short-term manufacturing output is positively impacted by power consumption (supply), but long-term manufacturing output is negatively impacted. As a result, the study found that Nigeria's manufacturing sector production was impacted by electricity usage and stated that a national economic plan was urgently needed to boost the industry's energy supply.

Omoroghomwan et. al., (2020). Observed the electric power outage cost to electricity distribution companies in Nigeria where financial implication in terms of potential revenue loss to the distribution companies as a result of outages on their distribution feeders was analysed. An important energy index such as Energy Not served (ENS) was used to estimate the consequent lost revenue based on the prevailing electricity tariff. From the analysed outage data, 4520 interruptions were experienced during the time under review. As a result, a total energy of 164,398,401.67kWh was not served which amounted to a loss of N4, 415,428,094.48 to the distribution company. Therefore, it was recommended the vandalization of power equipment should be sanctioned. Also, routine preventive maintenance and capacity increment on their network should be carried out.

Robert and Karen (2020) undertook a research to assess the effect of power instability on the profitability of industrial SMEs in Trans-amadi industrial area of Port Harcourt, Nigeria using a primary data. 112 Out of the 150 sampled companies that had audited records were studied over a 4-year period (2015-2019) to test the multivariate regression models. It was established the natural log of cost of alternative power does not significantly affect operating profit and that power supply ratio does not have significant effect on the net profit of the SMEs within the study period.

Adewuyi & Emmanuel (2021) assessed the effect of self-generation on firm performance across the six geo-political zones. The study employed a cross sectional Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS) techniques using the World Bank

Enterprise Survey (WBES). The result of the findings indicates that, bribery does not mitigate the effect of electricity outages on firms across all the geo-political zones in Nigeria with exception of the North-East and the South-East geo-political zones. Although, electricity outage is relatively low in the North-East region, further findings revealed that; firms in the south-east region experience the highest outage intensity of an average of 122.025 times in a typical month, while those in the South-South region experience the lowest outage intensity of an average of 25.845times in a typical month.

Ebhota and Tabakov (2021) X-rays the past and present power situation in Nigeria, the determinants of the amount of power demanded, and the several interventions in the Nigerian power supply. It was reported in the study population, industry, transportation, agriculture, and commercial services are the main determinants of energy demand in Nigeria. The study reveals that population interconnects all other factors and hence the major determinant of electricity supply. Industrial, transportation and residential sectors consume the most energy in Nigeria. It is concluded that effective power supply depend on careful and logical handling of the critical power technical activities such as power generation, efficient power transmission to users, efficient power distribution to the users, reasonable level of domestic power equipment manufacturing infrastructure, management of population growth and national power infrastructural development planning and enabling policy for power sector investments.

Ene et al. (2022) investigated the impact of electricity supply on manufacturing output in Nigeria between 1980 and 2019. The study employed an autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL). The result of the study revealed that electricity supply has a negative and insignificant relationship with manufacturing sector output, whereas technology has a positive and significant relationship with manufacturing sector output in the long run, and the paper recommends that adequate and stable supply of electricity and deploying modern technology should be on the front burner of the country's development policy.

2.1 THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

The resource dependence theory was developed by Pfeffer and Salancik (1978) to describe how an organization's behavior is influenced by the external resources it possesses. They suggest that in order for businesses to have access to the resources they require to survive,

they should both alter and bargain with their external environment. This implies that a firm's ability to compete is based on how well it manages its external resources.

The "Resource Dependency Theory" can be used to analyze how manufacturing performance is affected by electrical power shortages. According to the Resource Dependency Theory, manufacturing firms need a variety of resources, such as electricity, in order to run their business efficiently. Manufacturing firms that experience power outages are forced to rely on backup generators and other potentially more expensive and unreliable power sources. The performance of the manufacturing firms could therefore suffer as a result of higher expenses and lower dependability. In conclusion, the "Resource Dependency Theory" contends that frequent power outages can cause production process disruptions and lower productivity, and hence the disruptions lead to a reliance on potentially expensive alternative energy sources, which raises costs and reduces reliability, ultimately affecting the performance of manufacturing companies.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study employed the use of time series data covering 37 years from 1985 – 2022. The estimation technique of the study is ARDL which is best suited for the study in capturing how electricity power outage affects manufacturing performance in the long-run and short-run dynamics as well as Engle – Granger causality techniques to reveal the direction of causation using probability of F-statistics. E-views 9.0 software was used to analyse the secondary data in estimating the relationship among the variables.

3.1 MODEL SPECIFICATION

For the purpose of this research, the model is specified as follows:

$$Y = f(K, L) \quad (1)$$

Where:

Y = output.

K= Capital.

L= Labor.

Augmenting the model to accommodate other key variables that affect manufacturing performance in

$$\text{Nigeria, } RGDP = f(ELC, ELG, LBE, GCF) \quad (2)$$

Where,

RGDP=Real growth domestic product (proxy to manufacturing output).

ELC =Electricity consumption.

ELG=Electricity generation.

LBE=Labor employed.

GCF=Gross Capital Formation (Proxy to Capital input)

Taking the log of [Equation 2](#) and transforming it into an econometric regression model to be estimated, gives;

$$\text{Log } GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Log } ELEC_t + \beta_2 \text{Log } ELG_t + \beta_3 \text{Log } LEP_t + \beta_4 \text{Log } GCF_t + \mu_t \quad (3)$$

β_0 = Intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Regression Coefficients

μ_t = Stochastic/Random error term

t = Time period

A priori expectation for the estimate parameters are $\beta_0 > 0$, $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$ and $\beta_4 > 0$. To verify theoretical and statistical validity of the estimated coefficient, unit root test was conducted using Augmented-Dickey Fully test (ADF). This was followed by the by *ARDL* to determine the long-run relationship (Bound test and F-statistics) and Engel - Granger Causality test. Secondary data was used sourced from World Development Indicators and statistical Bulletin, were extracted for 37 years period.

4. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 CORRELATION ANALYSIS

Table 1: Pair wise correlation result.

Variables	LGDP	LELC	LELG	LLEP	LGCF
LGDP	1.000				
LELC	-0.699	1.000			
LELG	0.973	-0.490	1.000		
LLEP	-0.557	0.525	-0.696	1.000	
LGCF	-0.2629	0.500	-0.139	0.685	1.000

Notes: LGDP = manufacturing firms; LEC = electricity consumption L EG = electricity generation; GFCF = gross fixed capital formation;

Table 2 above indicates that performance of manufacturing firms output proxied by (LGDP) is negatively correlated with gross capital formation (LGCF), electricity consumption (LELC) and labor employment (LLEP) respectively. Indicating a weak correlation exist among the variables. However, the same performance of manufacturing firms output proxied by (LGDP) was found to be positively correlated with electricity generation (LEG) showing a strong relationship revealing LEG impacts positively on LGDP. Similarly, electricity consumption (ELC) is positively correlated with labor employment (LEP) and Gross capital formation (GCF). In the same vein, electricity generation (LEG) is found to be negatively correlated with electricity consumption (ELC), labor employment (LEP) and gross capital formation respectively while labor employment (LEP) and gross capital formation are positively related with electricity consumption (LEC) and negatively related with electricity generation (ELG).

Positive correlation among above variables indicated similar movement in the same direction implying electricity power outage impacts positively on manufacturing performance in Nigeria while negative correlation indicated dissimilar movement in different directions among the variables revealed that electricity power outage impacted negatively on Nigeria's manufacturing performance.

4.2 UNIT ROOT TESTS FOR THE VARIABLES

Table 2: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test of unit roots.

Variables	Level	First Difference	ADF Critical 5 %	P-Values	Order of Integration	Remark
LGDP	-0.712	-5.904	-3.633 -2.948		I(1)	Integrated of order one
LELC	-0.329	-5.918	-3.632 -2.941		I(1)	Integrated of order one
LELG	-42.485	-6.230	-3.653 -2.957		I(0)	Integrated of order zero
LGCF	-0.288	-4.263	-3.653 -2.957		I(1)	Integrated of order one
LLEP	-3.425	-3.399	-2.639 -2.951		I(0)	Integrated of order zero

Notes: LGDP = manufacturing sector output; LLEC = electricity consumption; LELG = electricit generation LGCF = gross capital formation; LLEP =labor employment

[Table 3 shows the findings of the unit root test.](#) it can be observed that LELG, and LLEP were found to be stationary at level, with ADF computed value of (-42.485 & -3.425) which are greater than the ADF critical values of -3.653 and -2.639 at 5 per cent in absolute terms. However, the manufacturing sector output proxied by (LGDP), electricity consumption (LELC), and gross capital formation (LGCF) were found to be stationary at first Difference with their ADF computed values of (-5.904, -5.918 & -4.263) respectively, which are found to be greater than ADF critical values of (-3.633 & -2.948), (-3.632 & -2.941) and (-3.653 & -2.957) at 1 and 5 percents in absolute terms respectively.

4.3 COINTEGRATION TEST

Table 3: Bounds tests for cointegration.

Model Specification	Period	Optimal Lag	F-Statistics
LGDP = f (LEC, LEG, LEP, GCF)	1985-2021	Sample Size= 36	6.327
<i>Critical Value Bounds</i>	<i>10% (Signif)</i>	<i>5% (Signif)</i>	<i>1% (Signif)</i>
I(0) Bound (K=4 variables)	2.45	2.86	3.74
I(1) Bound (K=4 variables)	3.52	4.01	5.06

Notes: K= number of explanatory variables; Signif. = significance level; n = number.

The cointegration boundaries test is displayed in Table 4 above. Using Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), the computed F-statistic of 6.327 is greater than the lower and upper bounds critical values of 2.86 and 4.01, respectively, at the five percent significance level. There is evidence of a long-term link between the variables, indicating that the null hypothesis that there is no cointegration is rejected.

4.4 ARDL SHORT-RUN DYNAMIC ESTIMATES

Table 4: Estimates of the short run coefficients.

Dependent Variable: Manufacturing firms performance				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-statistic	Prob.
D(LGDP(-1))	0.905	0.786	1.152	0.267
D(LGDP(-2))	-3.862	0.958	-4.030	0.001
D(LELC)	-12.585	3.094	-4.068	0.001
D(LELC(-1))	0.653	0.422	1.547	0.144
D(LELC(-2))	-0.404	0.446	-0.905	0.381
D(LELC(-3))	13.324	2.872	4.639	0.000
D(LELG)	-19.163	4.732	-4.049	0.001
D(LGCF)	-1.508	2.449	-0.615	0.548
D(LLEP)	1093.071	271.197	4.031	0.001
D(LLEP(-1))	-985.839	231.214	-4.264	0.001
CointEq(-1)	-1.045	0.763	1.368	0.193

Notes: Std. = standard error; Prob. = probability.

The short-run coefficients of the equations are displayed in Table 5 above. The estimates of the present value of electricity consumption (ELC) are statistically significant at 5% with a P-value of 0.001. This means that ELC seems to have a big effect on manufacturing performance in the short term during the study period. Furthermore, it was shown that the two- and one-year lags of electricity consumption (ELC) had negative significant coefficients (-0.404 and 0.653) and positive insignificant coefficients (0.653), which had

an adverse effect on manufacturing performance. Furthermore, it was discovered by (13.324) that the three-year lag of ELC had a positive and significant impact on manufacturing performance on average. It was discovered that the gross capital formation (GCF) had a large negative coefficient. It is implied that, on average, a unit increase in gross capital formation tends to result in a -1.508 decline in manufacturing performance. The results of the study revealed that labor employment was both positive and significant. This means that an average increase in labor employment (LEP) tends to increase manufacturing performance by 1093.071. Conversely, a one-year lag in labor employment (LEP) is found to have a negative but significant impact on manufacturing performance over the short term period. Furthermore, the coefficient of cointegration term has the expected sign—negative—but is statistically insignificant. Because of the cointegrating data's modest speed of adjustment—roughly 40.28 percent in the near term—no long-term relationship has been shown.

4.5 ARDL LONG-RUN ESTIMATES

Table 5: Estimates of the long run coefficients.

Dependent Variable: Manufacturing firms Performance				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	T-statistic	Prob.
LELC	-13773	8.275	-1.664	0.118
LELG	-1.650	2.041	-0.808	0.432
LGCF	5.879	4.394	1.338	0.202
LLEP	-10.757	14.977	-1.718	0.484
C	126.855	190.427	0.666	0.516

Notes: Std. Error = standard error; Prob. = probability; C = constant. Using eviews 9.0

The long-run coefficients of the equation are presented in [Table 6 above](#). The GCF was found to have an expected sign, while the ELC, ELG, and LEP do not conform to theoretical economic expectations. Indicating that the entire variable was found to be

insignificant, justifying the short-run dynamics. Observably, electricity consumption (ELC) and electricity generation (ELG), our variables of interest and a key factor contributing to manufacturing performance, have a negative coefficient and are insignificant, indicating no long-run association among the variables, confirming an insignificant co-integrating short-run equation.

The findings show that electricity consumption (ELC), electricity generation (ELG), and gross capital formation (GCF) are inversely related to the manufacturing performance proxied by GDP. This is contrary to a priori expectations, meaning that a unit increase in ELC, ELG, and GCF leads to a decrease in manufacturing performance of 12.585, 19.163, and 1.58, respectively. However, the results of LEP conform to theoretical expectations, meaning that a unit rise in LEP causes a 109.073 increase in manufacturing performance.

From the above illustration, ELC, ELG, and LEP are statistically significant at 1% for the period under review. On the other hand, GCF is statistically insignificant at 5%. R² with a value of 0.94 implies that only about 94.5% of the total variation in GDP is explained by the explanatory variable. Thus, the model has goodness of fit.

4.6 CAUSALITY ANALYSIS

Table 6: Pair wise granger causality test

Years	Hypothesis (H ₀)	Probability of F- Statistics
1985 - 2022	1. H ₀ : GDP \rightarrow LEC	0.0072 **
	2. H ₀ : LEP \rightarrow LEG	0.0408**
	3. H ₀ : LEP \rightarrow GCF	0.0075*

Source: Researcher's Computation using Eviews (9.0) Software. * = 1%, & ** = 5%

Table 7 shows the result of the pair wise granger causality test. Based on the decision rule, the alternative hypothesis that real GDP granger cause electricity consumption (LEC) is accepted since the null hypothesis is rejected. Similarly, hypothesis 2 shows the acceptance of null hypothesis indicating causality running from labor employment (LEP)

to electricity generation (*LEG*). Additionally, hypothesis 3 shows the rejection of null hypothesis revealing labor employment (*LEP*) granger cause gross capital formation (*GCF*) at 1% level of significance looking at their p-values concluding there is evidence of uni directional causality running from GDP to LEG, LEP to LEG and LEP to GCF respectively.

4.7 DIAGNOSTIC CHECKS

Table 7: Residual normality test.

Specification	Statistics	Probability	Conclusion
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	2.972	0.226	Evidence of Normality

Notes: H₀: Residual is multivariate normal; H₁: Residual is not multivariate normal.

Table 8: presents the residual normality test. The Jacque Bera's statistics value of 2.972 and probability value of 0.226, greater than 0.05 levels, the study accepts the null hypothesis, which specified that the residual is normally distributed.

Diagram 1: Cussum model Stability test

The model stability test

with the CUSUM residual test is shown in Figure 3. As can be observed, the model is stable according to the CUSUM stability test result. Because both of the CUSUM lines are between the two 5-percent lines, the model is stable.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Using time series data spanning from 1985 to 2022, the paper empirically examines the impact of electricity power outage on the performance of manufacturing performance in the Nigerian. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test, auto regressive distributed lag model (ARDL), and causality analysis were used to examine the time series data. The study discovered evidence of a short-run relationship between electricity power outage proxied by RGDP and manufacturing performance in Nigeria. Whereas, the study further revealed a unidirectional causality running from *GDP* to *LEG*, *LEP* to *LEG* and *LEP* to *GCF* respectively. Additionally, the study showed that Nigeria's manufacturing performance throughout the assessment period was negatively, albeit statistically significant, impacted by electricity consumption (ELC). Consequently, it was recommended that sufficient supply of power is essential not only for the expansion of the manufacturing performance but also for the nation's general economic development, opening the door for quick economic progress and helping Nigeria reach its full potential.

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